

Dioxouranium complexes of 2,2'-dihydroxyazobenzene : Binding of mono- and bidentate Lewis bases

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Uranyl complexes of 2,2'-dihydroxyazobenzene (H_2L) and its adducts with monodentate (B) and bidentate (B-B) Lewis bases of the type $[UO_2L.B.H_2O]$ (B = py, γ -pic, imz, dmf, dmsO, tppo) and $[UO_2L(B-B)]$ (B-B = bpy, ophen, dpa) are described. The complexes are pentagonal bipyramidal. The five coordination positions on the equator are occupied by the combination of ligand L^- , B, H_2O or B-B.

2,2'-Dihydroxyazobenzene (H_2L ; a) is a tridentate O,N,O donor and are effective agents for the stabilization of higher valent metal oxidation states^{1,2}. Many of these complexes act as model compounds of biochemical interests² and asymmetrically substituted ligands form isomeric complexes³. The ligand has been used in the development of chemistry of *d*-block elements¹⁻⁵ and remains unknown to explore actinide chemistry. There are few report on chemistry of heterocyclic azo dyes^{6,7} and azophenolatocarboxylates⁸ of uranium. In this presentation some new UO_2^{II} complexes of H_2L and their adducts are described.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of uranyl acetate with H_2L in presence of LiOH results $[UO_2L].3H_2O$ (1). The adducts belong to $[UO_2L.B.H_2O]$ (where B = py (2), γ -pic (3), imz (4), dmf

(5), dmsO (6), tppo (7)), and $[UO_2L.B-B]$ (B-B = bpy (8), ophen (9), dpa (10)) and were prepared by reacting 1 with respective bases. Complexes 2, 3, 5-9 are moderately soluble in chloroform while 1 and 4 almost insoluble but soluble in DMSO, DMF.

IR and electronic spectra : The IR ligand band at ~ 3000 cm^{-1} (phenolic O-H)⁹ is absent in the complexes. The broad band centred at 3370 cm^{-1} in the spectra of 1-8 is due to ν_{O-H} of coordinated water¹⁰. The ν_{C-O} (phenolic) ligand band ($1310-1320$ cm^{-1}) is shifted to higher energy by $20-30$ cm^{-1} on coordination with uranium¹¹. The N=N mode of the free ligand at 1560 cm^{-1} is red-shifted by $30-70$ cm^{-1} in the complexes, suggesting coordination of the metal ions to the azo nitrogen¹¹. The stretching at $540-570$ cm^{-1} is assigned to ν_{U-O} (phenolic). The complexes exhibit a strong stretch at $890-930$ cm^{-1} ($O=U=O$) and the force constant (f_{U-O}) in the range $6.58-7.13$ mdyne/A. The U=O bond length has been calculated¹² and the present values ($1.71-1.74$ Å) are in the expected range of $1.60-1.92$ Å. The ν_{N-H} in adducts $[UO_2L.imz.H_2O]$ (4) and $[UO_2L.dpa]$ (10) appears at 3490 and 3250 cm^{-1} , respectively, and shifted to higher energy relative to their non-coordinated values¹³. In 5, 6 and 7, the $\nu_{C=O}$ of dmf, $\nu_{S=O}$ of dmsO and

Table 1. ¹H NMR spectra of complexes^{a,b}

Compd. no.	δ (ppm), J (Hz)							
	3-H ^c	4-H ^d	5-H ^d	6-H ^c	3'-H ^c	4'-H ^d	5'-H ^d	6'-H ^c
1	7.90 (8.0)	7.48 (8.0)	7.55 (8.0)	7.98 (8.0)	6.98 (8.0)	6.70 (8.0)	6.83 (8.0)	7.18 (8.0)
2	7.76 (8.0)	7.34 (8.0)	7.43 (8.0)	7.82 (8.0)	6.81 (8.0)	6.55 (8.0)	6.66 (8.0)	7.04 (8.0)
3	7.72 (8.0)	7.30 (8.0)	7.41 (8.0)	7.80 (8.0)	6.78 (8.0)	6.50 (8.0)	6.62 (8.0)	7.00 (8.0)
4	7.60 (8.0)	7.24 (8.0)	7.36 (8.0)	7.71 (8.0)	6.68 (8.0)	6.38 (8.0)	6.50 (8.0)	6.92 (8.0)
8	7.92 (8.0)	7.45 (8.0)	7.58 (8.0)	7.99 (8.0)	7.14 (8.0)	6.90 (8.0)	7.00 (8.0)	7.40 (8.0)
9	7.96 (8.0)	7.54 (8.0)	7.64 (8.0)	8.04 (8.0)	7.17 (8.0)	6.94 (8.0)	7.09 (8.0)	7.51 (8.0)

^aAtom numbering scheme is shown in structure, ^bSolvent : CDCl₃ for 2, 3, 8, 9 ; DMSO-d₆ for 1, 4. ^cDoublet. ^dTriplet.

$\nu_{P=O}$ of tppo, respectively, red-shifted than that of individual free ligand values. This supports that these bases are bonded through oxygen to the uranium atom¹⁴.

The UV-VIS spectrum of H_2L in $CHCl_3$ solution shows three transitions at 250, 310 and 360 nm which refer to intraligand charge transfer bands. In the complexes, in addition to intraligand transitions, new bands appear in the range 420–460 nm due to apical oxygen $\rightarrow f^0$ transition within uranyl entity¹⁵.

¹H NMR spectra : ¹H NMR spectral data of the compounds are given in Table 1. The dianionic ligand binds to UO_2 moiety giving five-member (A-ring) and six-member (B-ring) chelate rings. Separate resonances were observed for the two aromatic rings in the ligand L^{2-} , confirming that the ligands are asymmetrically coordinated^{5,16} (structure b). The A-ring protons suffer a downfield shifting in comparison to B-ring protons¹⁷. Two protons (3,6, 3',6') are of doublet structures and two other protons (4,5, 4',5') of triplet type. The signals of 3-H and 3'-H are at higher field in view of the electronic releasing effect of phenolic-O function¹⁸. The pyridine-H in 2 and 3 are well characterised. The imidazole N-H in 4 appeared as a broad weak band at most downfield position (10.30 ppm) and other imidazolic protons are downfield - shifted relative to free ligand position. The bipyridine-H 8 and *o*-phenanthroline-H 9 appear at downfield position relative to A-ring protons and two halves are non-equivalent¹⁹, that may be due to ring size effect of this coligand L^{2-} .

Thermogravimetric studies : The complexes were subjected to thermogravimetric measurements in air atmosphere under nonisothermal conditions. The general behaviour consists of endothermic loss of H_2O , B or B-B in one or more steps followed by highly exothermic oxidative loss of the ligand above 450°. The final residue is invariably U_3O_8 ²⁰. In complex 1, mass-loss starts at 55° and ends at 180°. The coordinated water and water of crystallisation could not be differentiated as both steps are overlapped. In complexes 2-7, the loss starts at >100° followed by the loss of B. $[UO_2L.tppo.H_2O]$ (8) experienced water loss at 130–220° and tppo release at 350–410° followed by the loss of tridentate ligand. Complexes with bidentate donors (8-10) were found to be extremely stable. The donors were lost at 300–450°. The species UO_2L produced is hygroscopic and could not be investigated further.

Experimental

Uranyl acetate, *o*-nitrophenol, γ -picoline (γ -pic), bipyridine (bpy), *o*-phenanthroline (ophen), 2,2'-dipyridylamine (dpa), triphenylphosphine oxide (tppo), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (dmf), dimethylsulfoxide (dmsO), imidazole (imz) and other starting compounds were of com-

mercial grade. 2,2'-Dihydroxyazobenzene (H_2L) was prepared by the reported procedure².

The elemental analysis was carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 analyser. Uranium was determined by standard procedure¹⁰. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 783, 883 and JASCO FTIR 420 spectrophotometers, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on Varian Gemini (200 MHz) and JEOL JNM-GX 270 FTNMR spectrometers. The thermal data were recorded on Shimadzu TG 40 and TG 50 instruments.

$[UO_2L.3H_2O]$ (1) : A solution of ligand H_2L (0.45 g, 2.1 mmol) and $LiOH.H_2O$ (0.185 g, 4.4 mmol) in ethanol (50 ml) was added with stirring to uranyl acetate dihydrate (0.9 g, 2.21 mmol) and the mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 2 h. The solution was then evaporated to half of its volume. The resulting brown solid was washed with ethanol and dried over $CaCl_2$ (yield 60%).

$[UO_2L.\gamma\text{-pic}.H_2O]$ (3) : To a suspension of $[UO_2L.H_2O]$ (0.27 g, 0.5 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added with stirring a solution of γ -picoline (0.5 ml) in ethanol (5 ml). The mixture was then heated with stirring for 1 h. The orange-brown solid formed on cooling was washed with ethanol, crystallised from $CHCl_3$ -EtOH (1 : 1, v/v) and dried over $CaCl_2$ (yield 72%).

Complexes $[UO_2L.pyH_2O]$ (2), $[UO_2L.imz.H_2O]$ (4), $[UO_2L.dmf.H_2O]$ (5), $[UO_2L.dmsO.H_2O]$ (6) and $[UO_2L.tppo.H_2O]$ (7) were prepared following the same method (yields 45–75%).

$[UO_2L.bpy]$ (8) : To a suspension of $[UO_2L.H_2O]$ (1; 0.27 g, 0.5 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added with stirring a solution of 2,2'-bipyridine (0.18 g, 0.5 mmol) in the same solvent (5 ml). The mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 30 min. The orange-brown solid that formed on cooling was washed with ethanol, crystallised from $CHCl_3$ -EtOH (1 : 1, v/v) and dried over $CaCl_2$ (yield 80%).

Complexes $[UO_2L.ophen]$ (9) and $[UO_2L.dpa]$ (10) were prepared by identical procedure (yield 75 and 84%, respectively).

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